

Systematic review on valuation uptake

Objective, scope, definitions and classification typology

What is the aim of the valuation uptake review in the Values Assessment?

Valuation practitioners use valuation methods that result in explicit valuation of nature's contributions to people, including ecosystem services. Are these taken up by stakeholder for informative, decisive or technical policy design purposes. "Uptake" of valuation outputs and procedures by stakeholders is different from use of valuation methods by researchers. The review will tell us what proportion of valuation studies – with their value types and methods for different parts of nature & biodiversity – are taken up and for what purposes.

Visualisation of the logic of the valuation uptake review

A published study with evidence of valuation uptake addresses hypothesis H1. That is what you are looking for, but there are a number of studies which are not valuation, valuation but not about ecosystem service (ES) nor nature's contributions to people(NCP), which also need to be counted by you. Our aim is to know the proportion of ES/NCP valuation studies (blue box) which has evidence of uptake (green box), and the proportion of uptake studies which have different purposes(circles). To do this there are three screening questions you will apply to the published literature:

1. Valuation study?	2. Valuation uptake?	3. Uptake purpose?
<p>1. Is it a valuation study or not? Is it valuation of Ecosystem Services (ES) or Nature's Contributions to People (NCP)?</p>	<p>2. Are the valuation intended for uptake or actually taken up? (cursory reference to uptake or uptake case)</p>	<p>3. Are valuation results intended for / actually taken up for informative, decisive, or technical purposes?</p>

Valuation uptake classification definitions

Study type	Use type	Description	Detailed criterion description	Study examples	Example link
Not ES/NCP Not valuation			NOT (a valuation paper of ES/NCP that assesses the importance of nature and ES to people or human-nature relationships)		
Valuation, not ESV/NCPV	Other valuation applications	Valuation not relating to ecosystem services nor nature's contributions to people	A valuation that does not address ecosystem services or nature's contributions <u>to people</u> or <u>human-nature</u> relationships . With reference to the Driver-Pressure-State-Impact-Response framework. A study quantifying D-P-S linkages is not ES/NCP because it does not quantify the Impact/Importance for, or Responses by humans. "Human-nature relationships" refer to the relationship between State-Impact-Response indicators..	Aslambakhsh et al. (2018) Global cost optimization of a mini-scale liquefied natural gas plant	https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2018.01.127
ES/NCP, Not valuation,	Not a valuation application to a case study (neither monetary, biophysical, qualitative).	Opinion, general, theory and concept development only	General discussion of ecosystem services and nature's contributions to people, human-nature relationships, and their importance, or value for society.	Pascual et al. 2017 Valuing nature's contributions to people: the IPBES approach	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1GG06lZByRsulJW_egJlx5pomZzootE5X
		Meta-analysis	Articles that conduct statistical analysis of valuation results and study design features, but do not produce any <i>new</i> (original) valuation results for ecosystem service /nature's contributions to people. (NB: if meta-analysis results are used in a particular context it is benefit transfer and a valuation application, below)	Christie et al. 2019 Understanding the diversity of values of "Nature's contributions to people": insights from the IPBES Assessment of Europe and Central Asia	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1NY17TFSUu_NHxl8Q4ggPeXfSpNUQ-OC
		Valuation guidelines	Papers providing guidelines for selection of valuation methods, but not valuation per se.	Harrison et al. 2017 Selecting methods for ecosystem service assessment: A decision tree approach	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeB

					MnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
		Analysis of use (or lack thereof)	<p>Article that assesses, discusses or analyses the uptake of ESV/NCP, or lack thereof. E.g. papers discussing the role of valuation methods in policy design.</p> <p>The analysis is focused on the potential for and/or limitations to utilisation by society of valuation of ecosystem services or nature's contributions to people, as explained by i.a.. (i) timeliness, (ii) salience, (iii) credibility (iv) legitimacy (v) process documentation and (vi) cost of studies (see definitions at the end of this doc).</p> <p>May mention application(s) of such innovations or challenges <u>in other studies</u>, but does not provide any new/primary valuation results itself.</p>	<p>Laurans et al. 2013. Use of ecosystem services economic valuation for decision making: Questioning a literature blindspot.</p> <p>Jacobs et al. 2016 A new valuation school: Integrating diverse values of nature in resource and land use decisions</p> <p>Jacobs et al. 2017 The means determine the end – Pursuing integrated valuation in practice</p> <p>Marre et al.. 2016 Is economic valuation of ecosystem services useful to decision-makers? Lessons learned from Australian coastal and marine management</p> <p>Viscusi, W. Kip, Identifying the Legitimate Role of the Value of a Statistical Life in Legal Contexts</p>	<p>https://drive.google.com/open?id=1378iSIWN27-mn-wYse2x9iAhT25XScAW</p> <p>https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ScU82JpQqjXdutggc4asm1wBqK m2oae</p> <p>https://drive.google.com/open?id=1qDfX9yvtU py5zGxbPjcy5aKsiHamof LO</p> <p>https://drive.google.com/open?id=1xcWeaPV0_ep2CAJxHFeGMGNAVQj-_BYa</p> <p>https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=3426763</p>
Valuation application of ES/NCP degree of	No reference to uptake	Method development and testing only	Methodology development, possibly applied to a given set of data or a real-life social situation, but with a method development purpose. No mention of uptake of valuation results in a social situation. Valuation studies which focus on statistical issues or econometrics tests of valuation study design, without any discussion of uptake for informative, decisive or technical purposes..	Borzykowski et al. 2019 Scope Effects in Contingent Valuation: Does the Assumed Statistical Distribution of WTP Matter?	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1W4ZsA1uQn7EWE_vUk8OEwSQ92bsYYthJ

valuation uptake	Cursory reference to uptake	A potential, expected, or wished for uptake of valuation outputs from a case study	A valuation case study. However, valuation uptake is only mentioned as a <i>possibility</i> , a <i>potential</i> role in policy-making or decision-making. Typically, uptake of valuation mentioned in introduction/conclusion, but not analysed (in methodology, results or discussion of results.).	Burkhard et al. 2012 Mapping ecosystem service supply, demand and budgets	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1xIY9CyNq mWCzASMaRj05VM5UY omx2foJ
	Uptake case	Researcher / practitioner initiated valuation study	ES /NCP valuations studies where the paper addresses the uptake of these by a group of stakeholders, in an experiment or a study organisation where researchers have themselves gathered or contacted stakeholders to discuss and convey the valuation results. It includes valuations where authors have influenced (or tried to) real-life decision-making processes, but through a dedicated participation process they themselves have organised. Study with no evidence of third party commissioning (third party = not the authors nor participants in the study). Typically uptake is analysed in methodology and results. Or, researchers initiated study, published results (e.g. in a report), and then values were taken up by third party stakeholders. This iteration is documented in the academic publication. Typically uptake is analysed in discussion section.	Kenter et al. 2016 Integrating deliberative monetary valuation, systems modelling and participatory mapping to assess shared values of ecosystem services Ranger et al. 2016 Forming shared values in conservation management: An interpretive deliberative-democratic approach to including community voices Fish et al. 2016 Making space for cultural ecosystem services: Insights from a study of the UK nature improvement initiative	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeB MnhWUyBKxKYfvzZeRr5 xkU05ho7t https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeB MnhWUyBKxKYfvzZeRr5 xkU05ho7t https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeB MnhWUyBKxKYfvzZeRr5 xkU05ho7t
	Uptake case	Stakeholder initiated valuation study	Documentation of the process by which valuation results are implemented by social actors. Evidence of implementation of valuation results for informative, decisive, technical purposes <u>after</u> the results have been produced by researchers. Studies directly commissioned by stakeholders, or picked up by them from existing publications e.g. to deliver responses to decision-making questions. Documents how valuation results have been influential or taken into account by third party stakeholders. Third party stakeholders are social actors who are not acting as participants in the study, nor the study authors. Can include ex post studies of outcomes /impact evaluation of decisions or	Marre and Billé 2019A demand-driven approach to ecosystem services economic valuation: Lessons from Pacific island countries and territories Naidoo et al. 2009.Economic benefits of standing forests in highland areas of Borneo:quantification and policy impacts. Barton et al. 2010 Economic benefits of large-scale remediation of contaminated marine sediments—a literature review	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1OCJdY2zVa lh4rFY4LLnVVG54Fa9t2J Lv https://drive.google.com/open?id=1qmYGF-R7wMQnScEEuZkPZuvc OWrxncw8

			<p>technical design of policies informed by the valuation. Evidence of third party uptake of valuation is clear when valuation results are documented by third parties, e.g. as observed changes in regulations, budgets, programmes and projects decisions, definition and choice of variants, decision to go / no go for a project, choice of location, etc.</p> <p>Typically uptake is analysed in methodology, results or discussion section.</p>		<p>https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ZUXX7kK9wgplVVRJ2HLHy2gq41br3nZ5</p>
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See tables at the end of this document for further definitions of analysis of uptake issues

Classification of valuation purposes (intended & actual)

A study which is valuation of ES/NCP must have at least one intended purpose / actual use. You will register the most important valuation intended purposes/actual use of the paper, and make a note in Google Forms if there are several purposes in a single paper that make it hard to identify the most important purpose.

General	Specific	Short description	Description	Typical valuation process/output indicating this purpose:	
Informative	Formative Affirmative	Value formation or affirmation (not used decisively or for technical purposes)	A paper that mentions ESV/NCPV valuation process as a resource for training and education, or a process used to help stakeholders form, express, or affirm importances of nature. The valuation setting is designed for the purposes of forming and answering research questions about values. Value formation / affirmation through participation in these studies is not used for any of the decisive or technical purposes below.	Kenter et al. 2016 Integrating deliberative monetary valuation, systems modelling and participatory mapping to assess shared values of ecosystem services	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
	Awareness raising	Advocacy and raising awareness of total value, trade-offs, conflicts, scenarios.	An article that suggests or advocates that ESV/NCPV results are influential, or should be influential in creating the awareness, with respect to the importance of environmental issues, ecosystems preservation, etc. i.e. where ESV reveals, demonstrates, suggests the importance of ecosystems for society, including where it brings conflict with other values. Not related to a specific policy or decision to be made.	Costanza et al 1997 The value of the world's ecosystem services and natural capital	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
	Justification (ex post of a decision)	Evaluation of existing projects and policies (ex post)	An article where ESV/NCPV is used to justify (or to challenge) <i>already made</i> decisions, <i>existing</i> projects, policies or instruments. The key criterion here is " <i>ex-post</i> ": evidence after the decision has been made, the policy adopted and implemented.	Munda and Russi(2008) Social multicriteria evaluation of conflict over rural electrification and solar energy in Spain	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
	Accounting & Indicators	Assessment of historic trends	An article where ESV is used for ecosystem accounts or single indicators to assess long-term historic trends, of physical or monetary ecosystem services. Can include first time demonstration of indicator with the intention	Fish et al. 2016 Making space for cultural ecosystem services: Insights from a study of the UK nature improvement initiative	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1a3U6ezcuDaE0pc

			of accounting over multiple periods. Studies that just value the current state with no mention of follow-up/trends/accounting perspective, are awareness raising.	Villamagna et al. 2014 A multi-indicator framework for mapping cultural ecosystem services: The case of freshwater recreational fishing	NUPYWG2pzjR5q52UYD http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2014.04.001 (upload to Google Docs)
Decisive	Recommendations & guidance	Guidances, strategies, plans	ESV/NCPV has been used to justify which values are considered in recommendations, strategies, guidance documents for decision-making (e.g. meta-analysis for guidance values, EIA guidelines, national strategies...)	Van Houtven et al. 2007 Valuing water quality improvements in the United States using meta-analysis: Is the glass half-full or half-empty for national policy analysis?	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
	Participation	Negotiation, arguments for discussion, shared norms & conflict resolution	ESV/NCPV has been used as a process to <i>organise or support the expression of preferences, opinions, positions</i> , of stakeholders or people in a context where a decision had to be made, and before it had to be made (<i>ex ante a decision</i>).	Garmandia et al 2010 Social multi-criteria evaluation as a decision support tool for integrated coastal zone management	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
		Formulation of decision problem and structuring	ESV/NCPV has been used as a process or an instrument to structure the expression of preferences, opinions or positions of stakeholders, by <i>formulating the options</i> under scrutiny.	Fish et al. 2016 Making space for cultural ecosystem services: Insights from a study of the UK nature improvement initiative	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1a3U6ezcuDaE0pcNUPYWG2pzjR5q52UYD
	Prioritization Trade-offs	screening alternatives	ESV/NCPV has been used to define and specify the alternatives to be considered in a decision to be made. Valuation has been used in benefit-cost analysis or multi-criteria analysis to identify a set of alternatives that pass some minimum criteria (e.g. net present value > 0)	Naidoo et al. ,2009.Economic benefits of standing forests in highland areas of Borneo:quantification and policy impacts.	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1qmYGF-R7wMQnScEEuZkPZuvcOWrxncw8

		ranking alternatives	ESV/NCPV has been used to rank alternatives considered in a decision to be made, a policy to be designed. E.g. by ranking alternatives by net present value in a CBA, or by total utility our outranking in a multi-criteria analysis.	Marre and Billé 2019A demand-driven approach to ecosystem services economic valuation: Lessons from Pacific island countries and territories Schleiniger 1999 Comprehensive cost-effectiveness analysis of measures to reduce nitrogen emissions in Switzerland	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1OCJdY2zValh4rFY4LLnVVG54Fa9t2JLv 10.1016/S0921-8009(98)00104-9 (upload to Google Docs)
	Environmental management criterion	Policy target-setting	ESV/NCPV has been used to specify, and especially quantify, the target of a given policy or instrument to be decided upon or implemented (e.g. thresholds, biological indicators, quality levels, compliance rates, reserve area target, restoration, conservation targets etc.).	Schroter et al 2014 Ecosystem Services and Opportunity Costs Shift Spatial Priorities for Conserving Forest Biodiversity	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
		Criteria for spatial targeting (zoning, planning)	ESV/NCPV has been used to produce a zoning and a spatial planning of environmental policies, instruments (prioritization of conservation objectives...). Mapping of ecosystem services as valuation.	Schroter et al 2014 Ecosystem Services and Opportunity Costs Shift Spatial Priorities for Conserving Forest Biodiversity Veidemane et al. 2017 Application of the marine ecosystem services approach in the development of the maritime spatial plan of Latvia	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t https://drive.google.com/open?id=1ak7mvYsvYfTshVuOPk7gHvb3kF2D9RZY
		Allocation of rights to land and natural resource use	ESV/NCPV to determine welfare from changes in operating, use, extraction, emissions rights regimes. Rights could include ownership / licencing / permitting / certification / quotas/ responsibilities / use norms and rules.	Temper and Martinez-Alier (2009)The god of the mountain and Godavarman: Net Present Value, indigenous territorial rights and sacredness in a bauxite mining conflict in India	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1EDJmWcCRirEnDkqqd7WEU2ZEfZ7ycbNq

Technical	Price-setting	Environmental standard setting (implicit pricing)	ESV/NCP has been used to value a physical minimum standard or conservation target: e.g. harvesting quota allocation, pollution emissions permits, reserve site selection	Schroter et al 2014 Ecosystem Services and Opportunity Costs Shift Spatial Priorities for Conserving Forest Biodiversity	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
		Pricing, setting incentive levels (explicit pricing)	ESV/NCP has been used to specify an economic parameter of an economic instrument: tax and fees rates, level of payment for ecosystem services. Explicit use for pricing: does not include payment instrument for eliciting willingness-to-pay (in CVM, CE studies) used to estimate welfare estimates.	Jack et al. 2008 A Revealed Preference Approach to Estimating Supply Curves for Ecosystem Services: Use of Auctions to Set Payments for Soil Erosion Control in Indonesia	https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1TdeBMnhWUyBKxKYfvzzeRr5xkU05ho7t
	Damage compensation	Establishing levels of damage compensation	ESV/NCP has been used to quantify the damages and the compensation required, in a legal process	Martin-Ortega et al. 2010 Application of a value-based equivalency method to assess environmental damage compensation under the European Environmental Liability Directive	https://drive.google.com/open?id=1U9--85VYfLK8lUT9eu-_q-uS2kKQN4cj

Cross read to blindspot review categories (Laurans et al. 2013)

The table identifies how the valuation uptake types correspond to types used in phase I of the valuation uptake review pilot (cross-read for reviewers who participated in that phase, but not relevant for new reviewers/students). “Valuation practitioners” are researchers or consultants who implement valuation methods.

Valuation uptake types «tentative labels»	Analysis of use	Cursory reference to use	Use case practitioner initiated study	Use case stakeholder initiated study
Empirical application of valuation	NO	YES	YES	YES
Analysis of uptake? (i)timeliness, (ii) salience, (iii) credibility (iv) legitimacy (v) process documentation and (vi) cost of studies (see table below for further definition)	YES	NO	YES	YES
<u>Evidence of</u> practitioner (supply) or stakeholder (demand) initiated valuation?	GENERAL	NO	PRACTITIONER INITIATED	STAKEHOLDER INITIATED
<u>Evidence of</u> implementation of valuation results by «third party» stakeholders for informative, decisive, technical purposes?	GENERAL	NO	NO	YES
Cross read to categories used in uptake review pilot and Laurans et al. (2013) valuation blindspot study	«Analysis of use issue»	«Cursory reference to use»	«Documented use case»	

Definition of issues in “analysis of uptake” studies

The table below lists issues that may be found in studies with analysis of uptake. These features may explain lack of valuation uptake, also referred to as valuation ‘blindspots’. Studies that go beyond cursory reference to uptake will contain a discussion of at least one of these issues and be called “analysis of uptake” studies.

Uptake issues	Description – lack of these éléments may explain lack of valuation uptake:
Timeliness	Delivering quality information when and where it is needed to assist progress in the decision/issue cycle
Salience	Addressing the options in the decision arena, including budgetary and legal consequences
Credibility	Building on a shared understanding of how things work, conditions and trends and prospects of consequences, through transparent methods with explicit assumptions and documented uncertainty
Legitimacy	Representing the interests of all legitimate stakeholders through composition of the team and transparency of the process followed
Process documentation	Independent assessment of the interface between valuation study stakeholders and users of the resulting products
Cost	Cost of information is less than and proportional to benefits of the decision under consideration